

An Aggressive Diagnostically Challenging CNS Malignant Neoplasm: Atypical Teratoid /Rhabdoid Tumour - 3 years Institutional Study in a Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Introduction: Atypical teratoid/rhabdoid tumors (AT/RTs) are rare and aggressive pediatric malignant rhabdoid tumors (MRTs) that occur within the brain characterized by biallelic loss of function alterations of SMARCB1.

Aim: The aim of this study is to find out the incidence of atypical teratoid/rhabdoid tumors (AT/RTs) for 3 years in our institute.

Objective: To analyse the demographic clinical and histopathological features of Atypical teratoid/rhabdoid tumors (AT/RTs).

Materials and Methods: It is a retrospective study conducted at Department of Neuro Pathology, Institute of Neurology and Neurosurgery, Madras Medical College / RGGGH, Chennai. 5 cases were reported from June 2016 to June 2019.

Results: Four cases of AT/RT reported in our institute were under one year of age. One case presented with drop metastasis. The incidence of AT / RT among CNS tumors in our institute is 1.60% and incidence among embryonal tumors are 15%.

Conclusion: Atypical teratoid/ rhabdoid tumor is a highly aggressive grade 4 tumor with poor prognosis. Five year survival rate is 14% and overall survival is 29%. So, it requires multimodality treatment approach.

Keywords: Atypical teratoid/rhabdoid tumor, SMARCB1.

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Introduction

Atypical teratoid/ rhabdoid tumour is a rare highly malignant embryonal CNS tumour characterized by biallelic loss of function alterations of SMARCB1. Commonly affects children less than 3 years of age. Accounts for 1-2% of paediatric CNS tumours. Male to Female ratio is 2:1. Most aggressive brain tumour of early childhood. It occurs in cerebral, cerebellar hemispheres, CP angle and brain stem.

AT / RT commonly seeds via the CSF pathway. Atypical teratoid/rhabdoid tumor was first described as a distinct entity in 1987. Rorke et al first recognized this tumor in CNS. AT/RT is accorded World Health Organization grade 4 in 2000 due to its high malignant potential.

Aim: The aim of this study is to find out the incidence of atypical teratoid/rhabdoid tumors (AT/RTs) for 3 years in our institute

Objective: To analyse the demographic clinical and histopathological features of Atypical teratoid/ rhabdoid tumors (AT/RTs)

Materials and Methods

It is a retrospective study conducted at Department of Neuro Pathology, Institute of Neurology and Neurosurgery, Madras Medical College / RGGGH, Chennai. 5 cases were reported from June 2016 to June 2019. All specimens received were fixed in 10 % neutral buffered formalin embedded in paraffin blocks and sections were stained with hematoxylin and eosin. Immunohistochemistry for INI1 was also performed.

Results

Four cases of AT/RT reported in our institute were under two years of age. One case presented with drop metastasis. The incidence of AT / RT among CNS tumors in our institute is 1.60 % and incidence

among embryonal tumors is 15 %. Out of 5 patients, 3 were male and 2 patients were female. Grossly the size of the tumour ranges from 1 to 2 cm. In 3 cases the tumours were located in the CP angle and other

2 tumours in the cerebral hemisphere. The CP angle tumours presented with paraparesis. The cerebral tumours presented with vomiting, paraparesis, lethargy.

Table 1: Incidence in our Institute in 3 years (June 2016 to June 2019)

Total CNS Cases: 1762		Total pediatric tumors: 296		Total Embryonal tumors: 34	
Non Neoplastic	Neoplastic	Benign	Malignant	Medulloblastoma	ATRT
528	1234	194	102	29	5
30%	70%	66%	34%	85%	15%

Table 2: Demographic & Clinico Pathological Features

Sl. No.	Age / Sex	Site	Size	Presentation
1	8 Months / M	CP Angle	1.5 cm	Paraparesis
2	1.5 Years / F	CP Angle	1 cm	Hemiparesis
3	2 Years / M	CP Angle	2 cm	Paraparesis
4	1.5 Years / F	Cerebral Hemisphere	1.8 cm	Vomiting , lethargy
5	5 Years / F	Conus Medullaris	2 cm	paraparesis

Case Series

- **Case 1:** Eight months male child presented with paraparesis, tumour location at cp angle with size of 1.5cm
- **Case 2:** One and half year female child presented with hemiparesis, tumour location at cp angle with size of 1cm
- **Case 3:** Two years male child presented with paraparesis, tumour location at cp angle with size of 2cm

Radiology

MRI

Figure 1: MRI shows solid mass with cystic component over left CP angle with obstruction of 4th ventricle and dilatation of 3rd and lateral ventricles

Case 4: One and half year’s female child presented with vomiting, lethargy, tumour location at cerebral hemisphere with size of 1.8cm

Gross

Tan pink to red soft tissue fragments with necrotic areas

Discussion

Atypical teratoid / rhabdoid tumour is a malignant CNS embryonal tumor composed predominantly of poorly differentiated elements and frequently including rhabdoid cells. Presence of rhabdoid cells with abundant mitosis is the most striking feature.

Primitive neuroectodermal component is represented by undifferentiated small blue round cells.

Mesenchymal component is represented by spindle cells with basophilic myxoid background. Epithelial component is represented as squamous and papillary differentiation.

Epithelial mesenchymal transition (EMT) is the defining feature. EMT appears to be crucial in the development and maintenance of chemo resistant

cancer stem cells. Chromosome 22q11.2 harbors the tumor suppressor gene SMARCB1. INI1 is a member of SWI2/SNF2 remodelling complex which is ATP dependent. Loss of function of this chromatin remodeling complexes is required for EMT. Aurora kinase A is an enzyme implicated in EMT and targeted therapies aim at inhibiting it. 75 % AT / RTs contain homozygous deletions of SMARCB1 or loss of one allele and mutation of other copy of the gene.

Figure 2: Squash Cytology : a) Pleomorphic cells arranged around the blood vessels (H&E 40X) b) Large cells arranged in acinar pattern (H&E 400X) c) Large and pleomorphic rhabdoid cells with abundant eosinophilic cytoplasm eccentric round nuclei and prominent nucleoli (H&E 400X) Images from left to right.

Figure 3: a) Tumour is composed of sheets and nests of neoplastic cells with areas of haemorrhage and necrosis (H&E 40X) b) Tumour also shows pseudopapillary pattern (H&E 100X) Images from left to right.

Figure 4: a) Perivascular arrangement of tumour cells (H&E 100X) b) Large and pleomorphic rhabdoid cells with abundant eosinophilic cytoplasm eccentric round nuclei and prominent nucleoli (H&E 100X) c) Tumour shows numerous mitoses (H&E 100X) Images from left to right.

Figure 5: a) Tumour stained positive for glial fibrillary acidic protein by immunohistochemistry b) Tumour stained positive for vimentin by immunohistochemistry Images from left to right.

Figure 6: a) Tumour stained positive for EMA by immunohistochemistry b) Immunostaining shows loss of nuclear staining of INI 1 and positive in the endothelial cells which serves as internal control Images from left to right.

Case 5: Case Report of a Patient with Drop Metastasis - An Unusual Presentation

5 years female child presented with weakness of both lower limbs of 2 weeks duration with deviation of angle of the mouth for one week. History of swelling in the back. Evaluated as a case of paraparesis.

Clinical diagnosis:

Multiple nerve root schwannoma (L5 – S1, D 10 / L 1)

Procedure done (D10 – L1 Laminectomy and excision of SOL)

Figure 7: MRI: PNET / Ependymoma in the lower dorsal cord / conus medullaris with leptomenigeal spread

Figure 8: a) Pleomorphic neoplastic cells arranged in diffuse sheets (H&E 100X) b) Large and pleomorphic rhabdoid cells with abundant eosinophilic cytoplasm eccentric round nuclei and prominent nucleoli (H&E 400X) Images from left to right.

Figure 9: a) Tumour stained positive for CK by immunohistochemistry b) Tumour stained positive for vimentin by immunohistochemistry c) Tumour stained positive for S100 by immunohistochemistry d) Immunostaining shows loss of nuclear staining of INI 1 Images from left to right.

Figure 10: 3 years incidence in our institute

Figure 11: Comparison with other studies

Molecular Insights

- ATRT is a disease intimately linked to epigenetic deregulation.
- ATRT can be grouped into three distinct major molecular subtypes, ATRT-MYC, -SHH and -TYR.
- Each of these is associated with distinct DNA-methylation and gene expression profiles as well as anatomic and clinical characteristics.

Figure 12: Molecular Insights

Conclusion

Atypical teratoid/ rhabdoid tumor is a highly aggressive grade 4 tumor with poor prognosis. Five year survival rate is 14% and overall survival is 29%. So it requires multimodality treatment approach.

Our case series helps in creating awareness of this complex tumor and stresses the importance of correct diagnosis. Also indicates the possibility of improved outcome with aggressive therapy.

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